

MOMENTS IN VOLTERRA BERGOMI AND BOUNDARY ATTAINMENT IN ROUGH HESTON

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ABSTRACT. We address two open questions in the Volterra volatility literature. First, we prove finite positive moments for the rough Bergomi price process, and for a wider class of Gaussian Volterra Bergomi models, in the whole subcritical range under negative correlation. More precisely, if $\rho \in [-1, 0)$, then $\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] < \infty$ for every $0 < p < p_\rho$, where $p_{-1} = \infty$ and $p_\rho = (1 - \rho^2)^{-1}$ for $-1 < \rho < 0$. For the fractional rough Bergomi kernel, this gives the finite side of the sharp critical moment threshold, complementing the known explosion result above the threshold. Second, we prove that the rough Heston variance process, equivalently the scalar Volterra square-root process with fractional kernel $K_H(t) = t^{H-\frac{1}{2}}/\Gamma(H+\frac{1}{2})$ and $H \in (0, 1/2)$, has a positive atom at zero at every positive time. Consequently, zero is hit with positive probability before every positive time horizon. This rules out any Feller-type condition making the zero boundary inaccessible in the fractional rough Heston model.

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1. INTRODUCTION AND MAIN RESULTS

Rough volatility models were introduced to reproduce the low regularity observed in volatility time series. The empirical analysis of Gatheral et al. [10] indicates that log-volatility behaves, over a wide range of scales, like a

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fractional process with Hurst index significantly smaller than one half. This led to non-Markovian stochastic volatility models in which the volatility factor is a Volterra transform of Brownian motion. Two benchmark models are the rough Bergomi model of Bayer et al. [4], which is lognormal and particularly useful for smile modelling and simulation, and the rough Heston model of El Euch and Rosenbaum [7], which belongs to the affine Volterra class of Abi Jaber et al. [1].

The first question considered here concerns moment finiteness in rough Bergomi. The risk-neutral price is a non-negative stochastic exponential. It is therefore a local martingale and a supermartingale, but its true martingale property and its higher moments are delicate because the volatility is lognormal and non-Markovian. Gassiat [9] proved that, in the rough Bergomi model, the price is a true martingale if and only if the correlation is non-positive, and that, for $-1 < \rho < 0$, all moments of order $p > (1 - \rho^2)^{-1}$ are infinite at every positive maturity. This leaves the finite side of the critical moment threshold. Critical moment indices also enter the model-independent wing formula of Lee [15], which makes subcritical moment bounds relevant for implied-volatility extrapolation.

The second question concerns the zero boundary in rough Heston. In the classical CIR and Heston models, the Feller condition is the standard criterion ensuring that the variance process remains positive. This condition is important both mathematically and financially: it controls whether the square-root diffusion can hit the degenerate boundary, it affects the interpretation of variance dynamics, and it influences numerical and calibration choices. For the fractional rough Heston variance process, the Volterra memory and the singular fractional kernel change the boundary mechanism. The affine Volterra framework gives existence, uniqueness in law and transform formulae; see Abi Jaber et al. [1], El Euch and Rosenbaum [7], and Friesen and Jin [8]. The result below shows that the classical picture does not survive in the fractional rough case: zero is hit with positive probability at every positive horizon, whatever the analogue of the Feller inequality. The question is also connected with the Feller-type tests for non-singular Volterra diffusions studied by Bondi and Pulido [6]. In the nonsingular regime, the kernel is smooth at the origin, the Volterra process remains a semimartingale, and boundary non-attainment can be studied through a path-dependent drift correction. This makes Feller criteria particularly useful for Volterra–CIR approximations of rough variance models, where positivity of the variance is a structural requirement for both the probabilistic model and numerical implementations. As a complement, the final subsection gives a resolvent-barrier refinement for smooth kernels, allowing a deterministic input curve $x_0(t)$ instead of a constant initial input.

1.1. Bergomi model and moment threshold. The rough Bergomi model is

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad S_t = S_0 + \int_0^t S_s \exp(Y_s) dW_s, \quad (1.1)$$

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad Y_t = y_0 + \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s \quad (1.2)$$

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad W_t = \rho B_t + \sqrt{1-\rho^2} B_t^\perp, \quad (1.3)$$

where $S_0 > 0$, $y_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, $\nu > 0$, $\rho \in [-1, 1]$, and B and B^\perp are independent Brownian motions. In the fractional rough Bergomi model, K is the Riemann–Liouville Volterra kernel $K_H(t) = t^{H-\frac{1}{2}}/\Gamma(H + \frac{1}{2})$. The analysis below is written for a more general class of non-negative convolution Volterra kernels. A finite maturity $T > 0$ is fixed. Volterra convolutions on $[0, T]$ are denoted by

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad (f * g)(t) = \int_0^t f(t-s)g(s) ds,$$

whenever the integral is well-defined. If μ is a finite measure on $[0, T]$, then

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad (\mu * f)(t) = \int_{[0,t]} f(t-s)\mu(ds).$$

Assumption 1 (Admissible Volterra kernel). The kernel $K : (0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the following conditions.

- (i) $K \geq 0$ and $K \in L^2([0, T])$.
- (ii) There exist constants $C_K < \infty$ and $\beta_K > 0$ such that

$$\forall h \in (0, T], \quad \int_0^h K(s)^2 ds + \int_0^{T-h} (K(s+h) - K(s))^2 ds \leq C_K h^{\beta_K}. \quad (1.4)$$

- (iii) There exists a finite positive measure \mathcal{R}_K on $[0, T]$, of the form

$$\mathcal{R}_K(dt) = q_0 \delta_0(dt) + q_K(t) dt, \quad (1.5)$$

where $q_0 \geq 0$, $q_K \in L^1([0, T])$, $q_K \geq 0$, and q_K is non-increasing, such that

$$\forall t \in (0, T], \quad (\mathcal{R}_K * K)(t) = 1. \quad (1.6)$$

The mass of the resolvent on $[0, T]$ is denoted by

$$|\mathcal{R}_K|_T = q_0 + \int_0^T q_K(s) ds. \quad (1.7)$$

For $\rho \in [-1, 0)$, the critical exponent is

$$p_\rho = \begin{cases} \infty, & \text{if } \rho = -1, \\ \frac{1}{1-\rho^2}, & \text{if } -1 < \rho < 0. \end{cases} \quad (1.8)$$

Theorem 1. *Assumption 1 is in force. Then, for every $p \in (0, p_\rho)$, with p_ρ defined by (1.8),*

$$\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] < \infty.$$

If, moreover, K is the fractional rough Bergomi kernel, then the sharp equivalence holds:

$$\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] < \infty \quad \iff \quad p \in (0, p_\rho), \text{ with } p_\rho \text{ defined by (1.8)}.$$

Remark 1 (Examples of admissible kernels). Assumption 1 is satisfied by the standard examples used below. First, let $K \in C^1(\mathbb{R}_+)$ be a non-negative non-singular convolution kernel which admits a first-kind resolvent \mathcal{R}_K satisfying the positivity and monotonicity requirements of item (iii) of Assumption 1; standard examples are the constant kernel and exponential kernels. Since K and K' are bounded on $[0, T]$, one has, for every $h \in (0, T]$,

$$\int_0^h K(s)^2 ds + \int_0^{T-h} (K(s+h) - K(s))^2 ds \leq C_T h.$$

Thus items (i) and (ii) of Assumption 1 hold, the latter with $\beta_K = 1$. Second, for $H \in (0, 1/2)$, the Riemann–Liouville rough Bergomi kernel

$$\forall t \in (0, T], \quad K_H(t) = \frac{t^{H-\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma(H + \frac{1}{2})}$$

satisfies Assumption 1. Indeed, $K_H \geq 0$, $K_H \in L^2([0, T])$, and the scaling $s = hu$ gives

$$\int_0^h K_H(s)^2 ds + \int_0^{T-h} (K_H(s+h) - K_H(s))^2 ds \leq C_{H,T} h^{2H}.$$

Moreover, define the Riemann–Liouville rough resolvent by

$$\forall t \in (0, T], \quad \mathcal{R}_H(dt) = \frac{t^{-H-1/2}}{\Gamma(1/2 - H)} dt.$$

Its density is non-negative, non-increasing, integrable on $(0, T]$, and the beta-function identity gives

$$\forall t \in (0, T], \quad (\mathcal{R}_H * K_H)(t) = 1.$$

Thus item (iii) holds, and Assumption 1 holds.

1.2. Rough Heston boundary. Let

$$H \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right), \quad v_0 > 0, \quad b \geq 0, \quad \kappa \geq 0, \quad \nu > 0,$$

and

$$\forall t > 0, \quad K_H(t) := \frac{t^{H-\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma(H + \frac{1}{2})}.$$

The rough Heston variance process is the scalar Volterra CIR process

$$V_t = v_0 + \int_0^t K_H(t-s)(b - \kappa V_s) ds + \nu \int_0^t K_H(t-s) \sqrt{V_s} dW_s. \quad (1.9)$$

In the usual rough Heston parametrization, $b = \kappa\theta$. Since $H > 0$, one has $K_H \in L^2_{\text{loc}}(\mathbb{R}_+)$, which is the natural threshold for the stochastic convolution in (1.9). The existence of a continuous non-negative weak solution, uniqueness in law, and the affine Fourier–Laplace formula are standard results for affine Volterra processes; see Abi Jaber et al. [1] for the general affine Volterra framework, El Euch and Rosenbaum [7] for the rough Heston characteristic function, and Friesen and Jin [8] for the Volterra square-root process.

Theorem 2 (Atom at zero and absence of a Feller non-attainment regime).
For every $T > 0$, one has

$$\mathbb{P}(V_T = 0) \geq \exp \left(-v_0 \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2} - H)^2}{\nu^2\Gamma(1 - 2H)^2} T^{-2H} - b \frac{8H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2} - H)}{\nu^2(1 - 2H)\Gamma(1 - 2H)} T^{\frac{1}{2} - H} \right) > 0, \quad (1.10)$$

The two coefficients

$$\frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2} - H)^2}{\nu^2\Gamma(1 - 2H)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{8H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2} - H)}{\nu^2(1 - 2H)\Gamma(1 - 2H)}$$

which appear in the exponent of (1.10) are positive because $H \in (0, 1/2)$. Theorem 2 shows that, for the fractional rough kernel, no inequality of the classical form $2\kappa\theta \geq \nu^2$ can make the boundary zero inaccessible. Indeed, even under such an inequality,

$$\forall T > 0, \quad \mathbb{P}(V_T = 0) > 0.$$

2. CONTROL OF VOLTEIRA BERGOMI MOMENTS: PROOF OF THEOREM 1

The proof of Theorem 1 is postponed to the end of this section. For $p > 1$ and $\rho < 0$, we introduce the tilted stochastic Volterra equation

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad \tilde{Y}_t = y_0 + \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s + \nu p \rho \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{\tilde{Y}_s} ds. \quad (2.1)$$

Since $p\rho < 0$, the last term is a negative feedback term. Local existence and pathwise uniqueness for (2.1) follow from the standard local theory for non-linear Volterra equations with L^1 -kernels and locally Lipschitz nonlinearities; see Gripenberg et al. [11, Chapter 12], and also Abi Jaber et al. [1, Appendix B] for the same convolution setting. The stopped Girsanov argument below reduces the moment estimate for S to an exponential-integrability estimate for \tilde{Y} .

Lemma 2.1. *Under the Assumption 1 is in force, for $p > 1$ and $\rho < 0$, if the solution \tilde{Y} of (2.1) satisfies*

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(\frac{1}{2} p(p-1) \int_0^T e^{2\tilde{Y}_t} dt \right) \right] < \infty, \quad (2.2)$$

then $\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] < \infty$.

Proof. For $R > 0$, the stopping time is

$$\tau_R = \inf\{t \in [0, T] : |Y_t| \geq R\},$$

with the convention $\inf \emptyset = T$. The notation $\tau = \tau_R$ is used. On $[0, \tau]$, the process $Z = e^Y$ is bounded. Since Y , Z , and τ are measurable with respect to B , conditioning on B gives

$$\mathbb{E}[S_\tau^p] = S_0^p \mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(p\rho \int_0^\tau Z_t dB_t + \frac{1}{2} p^2 (1 - \rho^2) \int_0^\tau Z_t^2 dt - \frac{p}{2} \int_0^\tau Z_t^2 dt \right) \right].$$

The stochastic exponential

$$\mathcal{E}_T^{p,R} = \exp\left(p\rho \int_0^\tau Z_t dB_t - \frac{1}{2}p^2\rho^2 \int_0^\tau Z_t^2 dt\right)$$

is a true martingale because the integrand $p\rho Z_t \mathbf{1}_{\{t \leq \tau\}}$ is bounded. Under the probability $\mathbb{Q}^{p,R}$ defined by

$$\frac{d\mathbb{Q}^{p,R}}{d\mathbb{P}} = \mathcal{E}_T^{p,R},$$

the process

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad B_t^{p,R} = B_t - p\rho \int_0^{t \wedge \tau} Z_s ds$$

is Brownian by Girsanov's theorem. Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}[S_\tau^p] = S_0^p \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^{p,R}} \left[\exp\left(\frac{1}{2}p(p-1) \int_0^\tau Z_t^2 dt\right) \right]. \quad (2.3)$$

Under $\mathbb{Q}^{p,R}$, the volatility factor satisfies

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad Y_t = y_0 + \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s^{p,R} + \nu p\rho \int_0^t K(t-s) Z_s \mathbf{1}_{\{s \leq \tau\}} ds. \quad (2.4)$$

The process \tilde{Y}^R denotes the solution of the full feedback equation driven by $B^{p,R}$, namely

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad \tilde{Y}_t^R = y_0 + \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s^{p,R} + \nu p\rho \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{\tilde{Y}_s^R} ds.$$

For every deterministic $t \leq \tau$, the restrictions of Y and \tilde{Y}^R to $[0, t]$ solve the same deterministic Volterra equation. By pathwise uniqueness,

$$\forall s \leq \tau, \quad Y_s = \tilde{Y}_s^R.$$

Consequently,

$$\int_0^\tau Z_t^2 dt = \int_0^\tau e^{2\tilde{Y}_t^R} dt \leq \int_0^T e^{2\tilde{Y}_t^R} dt.$$

The law of $B^{p,R}$ under $\mathbb{Q}^{p,R}$ is Brownian, so \tilde{Y}^R has the same law as \tilde{Y} . Assumption (2.2) and (2.3) yield a constant $C_{p,T} < \infty$, independent of R , such that

$$\mathbb{E}[S_{\tau_R}^p] \leq C_{p,T}.$$

By continuity of Y , $\tau_R \uparrow T$ a.s. Since S is continuous and positive, $S_{\tau_R}^p \rightarrow S_T^p$ a.s., and Fatou's lemma gives

$$\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] \leq \liminf_{R \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[S_{\tau_R}^p] < \infty.$$

□

Lemma 2.2 (Volterra chain rule). *Assumption 1 is in force. For every $h \in L^2([0, T])$, with $X = K * h$, and every convex function $\phi \in C^1(\mathbb{R})$, one has*

$$\forall \tau \in [0, T], \quad \int_0^\tau \phi'(X_t) h_t dt \geq (\mathcal{R}_K * (\phi(X) - \phi(0))) (\tau). \quad (2.5)$$

In particular,

$$\forall \tau \in [0, T], \quad \int_0^\tau e^{X_t} h_t dt \geq -|\mathcal{R}_K|_T. \quad (2.6)$$

Proof. The case $\tau = 0$ is immediate.

Step 1: Stieltjes differentiation formula. We choose the right-continuous non-increasing version of q_K . Its Stieltjes measure is denoted by μ_K :

$$\mu_K((u, v]) = q_K(u) - q_K(v), \quad 0 < u < v \leq T.$$

For $z \in C^1([0, T])$ and $z_0 = 0$, standard Stieltjes integration-by-parts calculations give

$$\text{dt-a.e.}, \quad \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * z)(t) = q_K(t)z_t + \int_{(0,t]} (z_t - z_{t-r})\mu_K(dr). \quad (2.7)$$

Step 2: Proof for smooth functions. Let $U \in C^1([0, T])$ with $U_0 = 0$, and set

$$F_t := \phi(U_t) - \phi(0).$$

Then $F \in C^1([0, T])$ and $F_0 = 0$. Hence formula (2.7) can be applied both to $z = U$ and to $z = F$. For $z = U$, it gives

$$\text{dt-a.e.}, \quad \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * U)(t) = q_K(t)U_t + \int_{(0,t]} (U_t - U_{t-r})\mu_K(dr).$$

For $z = F$, it gives

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dt-a.e.}, \quad \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * F)(t) &= q_K(t)F_t + \int_{(0,t]} (F_t - F_{t-r})\mu_K(dr) \\ &= q_K(t)(\phi(U_t) - \phi(0)) + \int_{(0,t]} (\phi(U_t) - \phi(U_{t-r}))\mu_K(dr). \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\mathcal{R}_K * U = q_0 U + q_K * U \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{R}_K * F = q_0 F + q_K * F,$$

we have

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * U)(t) = q_0 \dot{U}_t + \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * U)(t),$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * F)(t) = q_0 \phi'(U_t) \dot{U}_t + \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * F)(t).$$

Therefore the atom contribution q_0 cancels in the difference:

$$\begin{aligned} &\phi'(U_t) \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * U)(t) - \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * F)(t) \\ &= \phi'(U_t) \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * U)(t) - \frac{d}{dt}(q_K * F)(t). \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the two identities obtained from (2.7), we get

$$\begin{aligned} dt\text{-a.e.}, \quad & \phi'(U_t) \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * U)(t) - \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * (\phi(U) - \phi(0)))(t) \\ & = q_K(t) [\phi'(U_t)U_t - \phi(U_t) + \phi(0)] \\ & \quad + \int_{(0,t]} [\phi'(U_t)(U_t - U_{t-r}) - \phi(U_t) + \phi(U_{t-r})] \mu_K(dr). \end{aligned}$$

Both terms on the right-hand side are non-negative by convexity. Hence

$$dt\text{-a.e.}, \quad \phi'(U_t) \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * U)(t) \geq \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * (\phi(U) - \phi(0)))(t).$$

Integration over $[0, \tau]$ thus gives

$$\forall \tau \in [0, T], \quad \int_0^\tau \phi'(U_t) \frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * U)(t) dt \geq (\mathcal{R}_K * (\phi(U) - \phi(0)))(\tau). \quad (2.8)$$

Step 3: Extension by causal smoothing. Since $X = K * h$ is not necessarily C^1 on $[0, T]$, the previous step cannot be applied directly to X . We therefore approximate X by causally smoothed paths. Indeed, take a non-negative $\zeta \in C_c^\infty(0, 1)$ with $\int_0^1 \zeta(s) ds = 1$, set $\zeta_\varepsilon(t) = \varepsilon^{-1} \zeta(t/\varepsilon)$, and extend all functions by zero to $(-\infty, 0)$. With

$$X^\varepsilon := \zeta_\varepsilon * X,$$

one has $X^\varepsilon \in C^1([0, T])$, $X_0^\varepsilon = 0$, and $X^\varepsilon \rightarrow X$ uniformly on $[0, T]$. Moreover, since $X = K * h$ and $\mathcal{R}_K * K = 1$,

$$\mathcal{R}_K * X^\varepsilon = \zeta_\varepsilon * (\mathcal{R}_K * X) = \zeta_\varepsilon * (1 * h),$$

and hence

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\mathcal{R}_K * X^\varepsilon)(t) = (\zeta_\varepsilon * h)(t).$$

Applying (2.8) to $U = X^\varepsilon$ gives

$$\int_0^\tau \phi'(X_t^\varepsilon) (\zeta_\varepsilon * h)(t) dt \geq (\mathcal{R}_K * (\phi(X^\varepsilon) - \phi(0)))(\tau).$$

Letting $\varepsilon \downarrow 0$, using $X^\varepsilon \rightarrow X$ uniformly, $\zeta_\varepsilon * h \rightarrow h$ in $L^2([0, T])$, and the finite mass of \mathcal{R}_K , gives (2.5). With $\phi(x) = e^x$, inequality (2.5) gives

$$\forall \tau \in [0, T], \quad \int_0^\tau e^{X_t} h_t dt \geq q_0(e^{X_\tau} - 1) + \int_0^\tau q_K(\tau - s)(e^{X_s} - 1) ds.$$

Since $e^x - 1 \geq -1$, the right-hand side is bounded below by

$$-q_0 - \int_0^\tau q_K(\tau - s) ds \geq -|\mathcal{R}_K|_T.$$

This proves (2.6). □

Lemma 2.3. *Under Assumption 1, the following facts hold.*

(i) For every $f \in L^2([0, T])$, the function $K * f$ has a continuous representative on $[0, T]$. Consequently,

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad G_t = \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s \quad (2.9)$$

has a continuous version on $[0, T]$.

(ii) Let μ be the law of G on $C([0, T])$. Its Cameron–Martin space is

$$\mathcal{H}_G = \{\nu K * f : f \in L^2([0, T])\} \quad \text{endowed with} \quad \|\nu K * f\|_{\mathcal{H}_G} = \|f\|_{L^2([0, T])}. \quad (2.10)$$

Moreover, $0 \in \text{supp } \mu$.

(iii) For every $a > 0$ and every $x \in C([0, T])$, the equation

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad Y_t^x = y_0 + x_t - \nu a \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{Y_s^x} ds \quad (2.11)$$

has a unique solution in $C([0, T])$. Moreover, the map $x \mapsto Y^x$ is continuous from $C([0, T])$ to itself.

Proof. Point (i) follows directly from the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality and the modulus condition (1.4). For the stochastic convolution, Itô’s isometry gives the corresponding L^2 -increment estimate; Gaussian moment equivalence and Kolmogorov’s continuity criterion then give a continuous version.

For (ii), the identity (1.6) implies injectivity of $f \mapsto K * f$. The displayed description of \mathcal{H}_G is the standard Cameron–Martin description for Gaussian Volterra convolutions with deterministic kernel; see, for instance, Lifshits [16, Chapter 2], Janson [12, Chapter 3], and Bogachev [5, Chapter 3]. Since μ is centred, its support is the closure of its Cameron–Martin space in $C([0, T])$, hence contains zero.

Finally, (iii) is an application of the standard local theory for nonlinear Volterra equations with L^1 -kernel and locally Lipschitz nonlinearity; see Gripenberg et al. [11, Chapter 12], and also the fixed-point arguments in Abi Jaber et al. [1, Appendix B]. The negative feedback term prevents explosion, since $K \geq 0$ gives the a priori bounds

$$Y_t^x \leq y_0 + \|x\|_\infty$$

and

$$Y_t^x \geq y_0 - \|x\|_\infty - \nu a e^{y_0 + \|x\|_\infty} \|K\|_{L^1([0, T])}.$$

Continuous dependence follows from the usual Volterra–Gronwall argument. \square

Lemma 2.4 (Cameron–Martin coercivity). *Assumption 1 is in force. Let $a > 0$, $\varepsilon > 0$, $g \in C([0, T])$ with $\|g\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon$, and $f \in L^2([0, T])$. If Y solves*

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad Y_t = y_0 + g_t + \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) f_s ds - \nu a \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{Y_s} ds, \quad (2.12)$$

then

$$\int_0^T e^{2Y_t} dt \leq \frac{e^{4\varepsilon}}{a^2} \int_0^T f_t^2 dt + \frac{2e^{y_0+\varepsilon}}{a\nu} |\mathcal{R}_K|_T. \quad (2.13)$$

Proof. The function $X = Y - y_0 - g$ satisfies $X = K * (\nu h)$, where

$$h = f - ae^Y.$$

Since $f \in L^2([0, T])$ and Y is continuous, $h \in L^2([0, T])$. Lemma 2.2, applied to νh , gives

$$\int_0^T e^{X_t} h_t dt \geq -\frac{|\mathcal{R}_K|_T}{\nu}.$$

Thus

$$a \int_0^T e^{X_t+Y_t} dt \leq \int_0^T e^{X_t} f_t dt + \frac{|\mathcal{R}_K|_T}{\nu}. \quad (2.14)$$

Since $\|g\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon$, one has

$$e^{X_t+Y_t} \geq e^{-y_0-\varepsilon} e^{2Y_t}, \quad e^{X_t} \leq e^{-y_0+\varepsilon} e^{Y_t}.$$

Therefore, by Young's inequality with coefficient $ae^{-2\varepsilon}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T e^{X_t} f_t dt &\leq e^{-y_0+\varepsilon} \int_0^T e^{Y_t} |f_t| dt \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} ae^{-y_0-\varepsilon} \int_0^T e^{2Y_t} dt + \frac{e^{-y_0+3\varepsilon}}{2a} \int_0^T f_t^2 dt. \end{aligned}$$

Inserted into (2.14), this gives

$$\frac{1}{2} ae^{-y_0-\varepsilon} \int_0^T e^{2Y_t} dt \leq \frac{e^{-y_0+3\varepsilon}}{2a} \int_0^T f_t^2 dt + \frac{|\mathcal{R}_K|_T}{\nu}.$$

Multiplication by $2e^{y_0+\varepsilon}/a$ proves (2.13). \square

Remark 2. The preceding inequality gives a deterministic control when the Brownian input is replaced by a Cameron–Martin direction. More precisely, for $\mathfrak{h} \in \mathcal{H}_G$, write

$$\mathfrak{h} = \nu K * f, \quad f \in L^2([0, T]).$$

Let $\tilde{Y}^{\mathfrak{h}}$ be the solution of

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad \tilde{Y}_t^{\mathfrak{h}} = y_0 + \mathfrak{h}_t + \nu p \rho \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{\tilde{Y}_s^{\mathfrak{h}}} ds. \quad (2.15)$$

Applying Lemma 2.4 with $a = -p\rho$, $g = 0$, and this choice of f , gives

$$\int_0^T e^{2\tilde{Y}_t^{\mathfrak{h}}} dt \leq \frac{1}{p^2 \rho^2} \|\mathfrak{h}\|_{\mathcal{H}_G}^2 - \frac{2e^{y_0}}{p\rho\nu} |\mathcal{R}_K|_T. \quad (2.16)$$

Equivalently, for every $\lambda < \frac{1}{2} p^2 \rho^2$,

$$\sup_{\mathfrak{h} \in \mathcal{H}_G} \left\{ \lambda \int_0^T e^{2\tilde{Y}_t^{\mathfrak{h}}} dt - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathfrak{h}\|_{\mathcal{H}_G}^2 \right\} < \infty. \quad (2.17)$$

At this point, one would like to approximate the Brownian Volterra input

$$G_t = \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s$$

by Cameron–Martin paths and to deduce the stochastic estimate (2.2) directly from (2.17). This is not a legitimate pathwise argument. A typical realization of G does not belong to \mathcal{H}_G , and the formal substitution $f = \dot{B}$ is meaningless, since Brownian motion has no L^2 -density. Even if one approximates G uniformly by Cameron–Martin paths $\mathfrak{h}^n = \nu K * f^n$, their Cameron–Martin norms typically diverge,

$$\|\mathfrak{h}^n\|_{\mathcal{H}_G} = \|f^n\|_{L^2([0,T])} \longrightarrow \infty,$$

so the deterministic estimate cannot be passed to the Brownian input by a simple approximation argument. The passage to the stochastic input is instead made through Borell’s Gaussian isoperimetric inequality. The deterministic Cameron–Martin estimate implies that suitable enlargements of a small ball by Cameron–Martin directions are contained in sublevel sets of

$$\Psi(x) := \int_0^T e^{2Y_t^x} dt.$$

More precisely, for an appropriate radius r_R ,

$$A_\varepsilon + r_R \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{H}_G} \subset \{\Psi \leq R\}.$$

Borell’s inequality converts this deterministic inclusion into a Gaussian tail bound for $\Psi(G)$.

Lemma 2.5 (Borell inequality). *Let E be a separable Banach space, μ a centred Gaussian measure on E , and H its Cameron–Martin space. If $A \subset E$ is Borel and $\mu(A) > 0$, then*

$$\forall r \geq 0, \quad \mu_*(A + r\mathcal{B}_H) \geq \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(\mu(A)) + r), \quad (2.18)$$

where \mathcal{B}_H is the closed unit ball of H , μ_* denotes inner measure, and Φ is the standard normal distribution function.

Proof. This is Borell’s Gaussian isoperimetric inequality in a separable Banach space, with enlargement in Cameron–Martin directions; see Ledoux [14, Theorem 4.3]. \square

Proposition 1. *Under Assumption 1, for $a > 0$, the solution of*

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad Y_t = y_0 + \nu \int_0^t K(t-s) dB_s - \nu a \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{Y_s} ds \quad (2.19)$$

satisfies

$$\forall \lambda < a^2/2, \quad \mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(\lambda \int_0^T e^{2Y_t} dt \right) \right] < \infty. \quad (2.20)$$

Proof. The law of G in (2.9) on $C([0, T])$ is denoted by μ . For $x \in C([0, T])$, Y^x denotes the solution of

$$\forall t \in [0, T], \quad Y_t^x = y_0 + x_t - \nu a \int_0^t K(t-s) e^{Y_s^x} ds,$$

and

$$\Psi(x) = \int_0^T e^{2Y_t^x} dt.$$

Lemma 2.3, item (iii), implies that Ψ is Borel. For $\varepsilon > 0$, the set

$$A_\varepsilon = \{x \in C([0, T]) : \|x\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon\}$$

has positive μ -measure because $0 \in \text{supp } \mu$. If $x \in A_\varepsilon + \mathfrak{h}$ with $\mathfrak{h} \in \mathcal{H}_G$, then

$$x = g + \mathfrak{h}, \quad \|g\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon.$$

By (2.10), one has

$$\mathfrak{h} = \nu K * f$$

for a unique $f \in L^2([0, T])$, and

$$\|\mathfrak{h}\|_{\mathcal{H}_G} = \|f\|_{L^2([0, T])}.$$

Lemma 2.4 gives

$$\Psi(x) \leq \frac{e^{4\varepsilon}}{a^2} \|\mathfrak{h}\|_{\mathcal{H}_G}^2 + \frac{2e^{y_0+\varepsilon}}{a\nu} |\mathcal{R}_K|_T. \quad (2.21)$$

For

$$R > \frac{2e^{y_0+\varepsilon}}{a\nu} |\mathcal{R}_K|_T,$$

the radius is

$$r_R = ae^{-2\varepsilon} \left(R - \frac{2e^{y_0+\varepsilon}}{a\nu} |\mathcal{R}_K|_T \right)^{1/2}.$$

Then (2.21) implies

$$A_\varepsilon + r_R \mathcal{B}_{\mathcal{H}_G} \subset \{\Psi \leq R\}.$$

By Lemma 2.5,

$$\mu(\Psi > R) \leq 1 - \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(\mu(A_\varepsilon)) + r_R).$$

For every $\delta \in (0, 1/2)$, the elementary Gaussian tail estimate

$$\forall r \geq 0, \quad 1 - \Phi(\Phi^{-1}(\mu(A_\varepsilon)) + r) \leq C_{\varepsilon, \delta} \exp\{-(1/2 - \delta)r^2\}$$

holds with a finite constant $C_{\varepsilon, \delta}$. Hence, after changing the constant,

$$\forall R \geq 0, \quad \mu(\Psi > R) \leq \tilde{C}_{\varepsilon, \delta} \exp\{-(1/2 - \delta)a^2 e^{-4\varepsilon} R\}. \quad (2.22)$$

If $\lambda < a^2/2$, then $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\delta \in (0, 1/2)$ can be chosen so that

$$\lambda < (1/2 - \delta)a^2 e^{-4\varepsilon}.$$

The layer-cake formula gives

$$\mathbb{E}_\mu[e^{\lambda\Psi}] = 1 + \lambda \int_0^\infty e^{\lambda R} \mu(\Psi > R) dR,$$

and (2.22) makes the integral finite. Since

$$\Psi(G) = \int_0^T e^{2Y_t} dt,$$

the proof is complete. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. For $0 < p \leq 1$, the non-negative local martingale S is a supermartingale, and $x^p \leq 1 + x$ on $[0, \infty)$. Thus

$$\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] \leq 1 + S_0 < \infty.$$

It remains to consider $p > 1$. Since $\rho < 0$, one has $-\rho\rho > 0$. The condition $p(1 - \rho^2) < 1$ is equivalent to

$$\frac{1}{2}p(p-1) < \frac{1}{2}p^2\rho^2,$$

because

$$\frac{1}{2}p(p-1) < \frac{1}{2}p^2\rho^2 \iff p(1 - \rho^2) < 1.$$

Proposition 1, applied with $a = -\rho\rho$ and $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}p(p-1)$, gives (2.2). Proposition 2.1 then yields $\mathbb{E}[S_T^p] < \infty$. This proves the subcritical implication under Assumption 1. In the fractional rough Bergomi case, the converse implication in the displayed equivalence is the complementary moment-explosion result of Gassiat [9]. \square

3. ABSENCE OF A FELLER CRITERION IN ROUGH HESTON: PROOF OF THEOREM 2

This section proves Theorem 2. The strategy is to study the Laplace transform of the rough Heston variance at a fixed time T , and then let the Laplace parameter tend to infinity in order to recover the mass at zero. By the affine Volterra transform formula, this Laplace transform is expressed in terms of the non-negative solution y_λ of a Riccati–Volterra equation. Using the first-kind resolvent \mathcal{R}_H of the fractional kernel, the exponential-affine formula can be rewritten in terms of two deterministic quantities only:

$$(\mathcal{R}_H * y_\lambda)(T) \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^T y_\lambda(s) ds.$$

The key point is then to obtain estimates on these two quantities uniformly in the Laplace parameter λ . This is done through a deterministic comparison argument: the Riccati–Volterra solution y_λ is dominated by the singular barrier

$$t \mapsto At^{-H-\frac{1}{2}},$$

for every $A > \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\nu^2\Gamma(1-2H)}$. Since $H < 1/2$, this barrier is integrable at the origin, and its convolution with the first-kind resolvent can be computed explicitly by the beta-function identity. This yields a strictly positive lower bound on $\mathbb{E}[e^{-\lambda V_T}]$, uniformly over $\lambda > 0$. Finally, since $V_T \geq 0$,

$$e^{-\lambda V_T} \longrightarrow \mathbb{1}_{\{V_T=0\}} \quad \text{as } \lambda \rightarrow \infty,$$

and dominated convergence gives a strictly positive lower bound on $\mathbb{P}(V_T = 0)$.

3.1. Preliminaries. For $\beta > 0$, the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral is

$$\mathbb{I}^\beta f(t) := \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} f(s) \, ds.$$

The Riemann–Liouville derivative of order $H + \frac{1}{2} \in (0, 1)$ is

$$\mathbb{D}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} f(t) := \frac{d}{dt} \mathbb{I}^{\frac{1}{2}-H} f(t),$$

whenever the right-hand side exists. More generally, for $a < t$, we use

$$\mathbb{D}_a^{H+\frac{1}{2}} f(t) := \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)} \int_a^t (t-s)^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} f(s) \, ds \right)$$

for the Riemann–Liouville derivative with lower integration bound a . The elementary identities used below are classical; see, for instance, Kilbas et al. [13], Samko et al. [17]. For $p, q > 0$,

$$\int_0^t (t-s)^{p-1} s^{q-1} \, ds = t^{p+q-1} \mathbb{B}(p, q) = t^{p+q-1} \frac{\Gamma(p)\Gamma(q)}{\Gamma(p+q)}. \quad (3.1)$$

It follows from the beta-function identity and the definition of \mathcal{R}_H in Remark 1 that

$$\forall t \in (0, T], \quad (\mathcal{R}_H * K_H)(t) = 1, \quad (3.2)$$

in the sense of Volterra convolution. We shall also use the special power identity

$$\mathbb{D}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} t^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\Gamma(-2H)} t^{-2H-1}. \quad (3.3)$$

Finally, we use the standard local regularization property of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals: if $f \in C^\gamma([a, b])$, $0 < \gamma < 1$, then $\mathbb{I}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} f \in C^{H+\frac{1}{2}+\gamma}([a, b])$ locally in the interior of $(a, b]$, with the convention $C^\rho = C^{1, \rho-1}$ for $1 < \rho < 2$. See Kilbas et al. [13], Samko et al. [17].

Lemma 3.1 (Resolvent form of the Laplace transform). *For every $\lambda > 0$ and every $T > 0$, there is a unique locally integrable non-negative solution y_λ of*

$$y_\lambda(t) = \lambda K_H(t) - \int_0^t K_H(t-s) \left(\kappa y_\lambda(s) + \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda(s)^2 \right) \, ds, \quad (3.4)$$

and

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{-\lambda V_T}] = \exp \left(-v_0 (\mathcal{R}_H * y_\lambda)(T) - b \int_0^T y_\lambda(s) \, ds \right). \quad (3.5)$$

Proof. The scalar square-root case of the Riccati–Volterra transform formula of Abi Jaber et al. [1], also used for the Volterra square-root process in Friesen and Jin [8], gives a unique locally integrable non-negative solution y_λ of (3.4) and the exponential-affine formula

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{-\lambda V_T}] = \exp \left(-v_0 \lambda + v_0 \int_0^T \left(\kappa y_\lambda(s) + \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda(s)^2 \right) \, ds - b \int_0^T y_\lambda(s) \, ds \right).$$

On the other hand, convolving (3.4) with the first-kind resolvent \mathcal{R}_H , using associativity of Volterra convolution and (3.2), gives

$$(\mathcal{R}_H * y_\lambda)(T) = \lambda - \int_0^T \left(\kappa y_\lambda(s) + \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda(s)^2 \right) ds.$$

Indeed, since $(\mathcal{R}_H * K_H)(t) = 1$, one has

$$\mathcal{R}_H * K_H * \left(\kappa y_\lambda + \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda^2 \right) = 1 * \left(\kappa y_\lambda + \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda^2 \right),$$

and evaluation at T gives the preceding integral over $[0, T]$. Substituting this identity into the affine transform formula yields

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{-\lambda V_T}] = \exp \left(-v_0(\mathcal{R}_H * y_\lambda)(T) - b \int_0^T y_\lambda(s) ds \right),$$

which proves (3.5). \square

Lemma 3.2 (Fractional maximum principle). *Let $0 < H < 1/2$, $a < t_0$, and $f \in C^1([a, t_0])$. If*

$$f(t_0) = \max_{t \in [a, t_0]} f(t),$$

then the Riemann–Liouville derivative with origin a satisfies

$$D_a^{H+\frac{1}{2}} f(t_0) \geq \frac{f(t_0)}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2} - H)(t_0 - a)^{H+\frac{1}{2}}}. \quad (3.6)$$

In particular, if $f(t_0) = 0$, then

$$D_a^{H+\frac{1}{2}} f(t_0) \geq 0.$$

This is the standard maximum principle for the Riemann–Liouville derivative, written with an arbitrary lower integration bound a ; see Al-Refai [2], Al-Refai and Luchko [3].

Lemma 3.3. *For every $\lambda > 0$, the function y_λ satisfies the following properties.*

(i) *One has*

$$\forall t > 0, \quad 0 \leq y_\lambda(t) \leq \lambda K_H(t). \quad (3.7)$$

(ii) *One has*

$$t \downarrow 0, \quad \frac{y_\lambda(t)}{t^{-H-\frac{1}{2}}} \longrightarrow 0. \quad (3.8)$$

(iii) *One has $y_\lambda \in C_{\text{loc}}^1((0, \infty))$ and*

$$\forall t > 0, \quad D^{H+\frac{1}{2}} y_\lambda(t) = -\kappa y_\lambda(t) - \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda(t)^2. \quad (3.9)$$

Proof. The non-negativity of y_λ is part of Lemma 3.1. Since the convolution term in (3.4) is non-positive, we immediately obtain

$$\forall t > 0, \quad 0 \leq y_\lambda(t) \leq \lambda K_H(t),$$

which proves (3.7). Hence

$$t \downarrow 0, \quad 0 \leq \frac{y_\lambda(t)}{t^{-H-\frac{1}{2}}} \leq \lambda K_H(t) t^{H+\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(H+\frac{1}{2})} t^{2H} \rightarrow 0,$$

because $H > 0$. This proves (3.8). It remains to record the local regularity and the fractional differential form of the Riccati–Volterra equation. Write

$$F_\lambda(t) := -\kappa y_\lambda(t) - \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda(t)^2.$$

Then (3.4) reads

$$y_\lambda = \lambda K_H + \mathbf{I}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} F_\lambda.$$

On every compact interval $[r, R] \subset (0, \infty)$, the function K_H is smooth and y_λ is bounded. By the local regularization property recalled above, a standard bootstrap gives

$$y_\lambda \in C_{\text{loc}}^1((0, \infty)).$$

Finally, applying $\mathbf{I}^{\frac{1}{2}-H}$ to (3.4) gives

$$\mathbf{I}^{\frac{1}{2}-H} y_\lambda(t) = \lambda + \int_0^t F_\lambda(s) ds,$$

because $\mathbf{I}^{\frac{1}{2}-H} K_H = 1$. Differentiating this identity yields

$$\mathbf{D}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} y_\lambda(t) = F_\lambda(t) = -\kappa y_\lambda(t) - \frac{\nu^2}{2} y_\lambda(t)^2,$$

which proves (3.9). \square

Lemma 3.4. *If $A > \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\nu^2\Gamma(1-2H)}$, then*

$$\forall \lambda > 0, \quad \forall t > 0, \quad 0 \leq y_\lambda(t) \leq At^{-H-\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (3.10)$$

Proof. We define $\bar{y}(t) := At^{-H-\frac{1}{2}}$. With

$$c_H := \frac{2H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\Gamma(1-2H)} > 0,$$

the formula (3.3) gives

$$\mathbf{D}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} \bar{y}(t) = -Ac_H t^{-2H-1}.$$

Since $A > \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\nu^2\Gamma(1-2H)} = \frac{2c_H}{\nu^2}$, one has, for all $t > 0$,

$$\mathbf{D}^{H+\frac{1}{2}} \bar{y}(t) - (-\kappa \bar{y}(t) - \frac{\nu^2}{2} \bar{y}(t)^2) = A\left(\frac{\nu^2}{2} A - c_H\right) t^{-2H-1} + \kappa A t^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} > 0. \quad (3.11)$$

The limit (3.8) implies $y_\lambda(t) - \bar{y}(t) < 0$ for all sufficiently small $t > 0$. If there were a time $t > 0$ such that $y_\lambda(t) > \bar{y}(t)$, continuity would yield a first contact time $t_* > 0$ such that

$$w(t) := y_\lambda(t) - \bar{y}(t) < 0 \quad \text{for } 0 < t < t_*, \quad w(t_*) = 0.$$

For every $\varepsilon \in (0, t_*)$, Lemma 3.3 gives $w \in C^1([\varepsilon, t_*])$, and Lemma 3.2 applied to w on $[\varepsilon, t_*]$ gives

$$D_\varepsilon^{H+\frac{1}{2}} w(t_*) \geq 0.$$

The relation between the Riemann–Liouville derivatives with origins 0 and ε is

$$D_0^{H+\frac{1}{2}} w(t_*) = D_\varepsilon^{H+\frac{1}{2}} w(t_*) - \frac{H+\frac{1}{2}}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)} \int_0^\varepsilon (t_*-s)^{-H-\frac{3}{2}} w(s) ds.$$

Since $w(s) < 0$ on $(0, \varepsilon]$, this relation implies $D_0^{H+\frac{1}{2}} w(t_*) \geq 0$. On the other hand, (3.9), the equality $y_\lambda(t_*) = \bar{y}(t_*)$, and (3.11) give

$$D_0^{H+\frac{1}{2}} w(t_*) = (-\kappa \bar{y}(t_*) - \frac{\nu^2}{2} \bar{y}(t_*)^2) - D^{H+\frac{1}{2}} \bar{y}(t_*) < 0.$$

This contradiction proves (3.10). \square

3.2. Proof of the Heston theorem.

Proof of Theorem 2. Fix $A > \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\nu^2\Gamma(1-2H)}$. Lemma 3.4 gives, for every $\lambda > 0$,

$$\int_0^T y_\lambda(s) ds \leq A \int_0^T s^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} ds = \frac{A}{\frac{1}{2}-H} T^{\frac{1}{2}-H}.$$

It also gives

$$(\mathcal{R}_H * y_\lambda)(T) \leq \frac{A}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)} \int_0^T (T-s)^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} s^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} ds.$$

The beta identity yields

$$\int_0^T (T-s)^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} s^{-H-\frac{1}{2}} ds = T^{-2H} B\left(\frac{1}{2}-H, \frac{1}{2}-H\right) = T^{-2H} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)^2}{\Gamma(1-2H)},$$

and therefore

$$(\mathcal{R}_H * y_\lambda)(T) \leq A \frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\Gamma(1-2H)} T^{-2H}.$$

Lemma 3.1 implies, uniformly over $\lambda > 0$,

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{-\lambda V_T}] \geq \exp\left(-v_0 A \frac{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\Gamma(1-2H)} T^{-2H} - b \frac{A}{\frac{1}{2}-H} T^{\frac{1}{2}-H}\right) =: c_T(A) > 0.$$

Since $V_T \geq 0$, one has $e^{-\lambda V_T} \rightarrow \mathbf{1}_{\{V_T=0\}}$ as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, and dominated convergence gives

$$\mathbb{P}(V_T = 0) = \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[e^{-\lambda V_T}] \geq c_T(A) > 0.$$

Since this holds for every $A > \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\nu^2\Gamma(1-2H)}$, letting $A \downarrow \frac{4H\Gamma(\frac{1}{2}-H)}{\nu^2\Gamma(1-2H)}$ gives (1.10). Finally, with $\tau_0 := \inf\{t \geq 0 : V_t = 0\}$, the continuity of the paths gives $\{V_T = 0\} \subset \{\tau_0 \leq T\}$, whence $\mathbb{P}(\tau_0 \leq T) \geq \mathbb{P}(V_T = 0) > 0$. \square

3.3. Improved Feller criterion for smooth kernels. Let us first recall the Volterra–CIR criterion obtained in Bondi and Pulido [6, Theorem 9]. For the non-singular Volterra square-root equation

$$X_t = x_0 + \int_0^t K(t-s)\kappa(\theta - X_s) ds + \sigma \int_0^t K(t-s)\sqrt{X_s} dW_s, \quad x_0 > 0,$$

with $K(0) < \infty$, their sufficient Feller-type condition for non-attainment of zero is

$$2\kappa\theta \geq K(0)\sigma^2.$$

This sufficient condition is generally not sharp in the genuinely Volterra case, because it does not exploit the favourable contribution of the memory term generated by the initial input. The result below refines this criterion in a resolvent form. Instead of treating only a constant initial value x_0 , we allow a deterministic positive input curve $x_0(t)$. The memory of this input produces an additional effective inward drift, measured by the quantity c_{K,x_0} . Consequently the classical CIR Feller drift $K(0)\kappa\theta$ is replaced by $K(0)\kappa\theta + c_{K,x_0}$, leading to a sharper barrier condition whenever $c_{K,x_0} > 0$. The point is that, when the kernel is smooth at the origin, the Volterra equation can be differentiated into a semimartingale equation with an additional memory drift. The estimate below keeps the favourable contribution of a deterministic input curve $x_0(t)$.

Assumption 2 (Smooth non-singular kernel). The kernel $K : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is a non-negative convolution kernel such that

$$K \in C^1(\mathbb{R}_+), \quad K' \in BV_{\text{loc}}(\mathbb{R}_+), \quad K(0) \in (0, \infty).$$

Moreover, K admits a non-negative resolvent of the first kind \mathcal{R} , that is,

$$K * \mathcal{R} = 1$$

in the sense of Volterra convolution. We assume that the kernel

$$-(K' * \mathcal{R})$$

is non-negative, non-increasing, locally of bounded variation, and satisfies

$$-(K' * \mathcal{R})(0) < \infty.$$

Proposition 2. *Under Assumption 2, let $x_0 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ be absolutely continuous on compact time intervals, and define*

$$c_{K,x_0} := \inf_{t \geq 0} \left(\dot{x}_0(t) - (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)x_0(t) + \int_0^t x_0(s) d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) \right).$$

Consider the Volterra square-root equation

$$X_t = x_0(t) + \int_0^t K(t-s)\kappa(\theta - X_s) ds + \sigma \int_0^t K(t-s)\sqrt{X_s} dW_s.$$

If

$$2(K(0)\kappa\theta + c_{K,x_0}) > K(0)^2\sigma^2,$$

then

$$\mathbb{P}(\forall t > 0, X_t > 0) = 1.$$

Proof. We set

$$dZ_t := \kappa(\theta - X_t) dt + \sigma\sqrt{X_t} dW_t.$$

Then

$$X_t - x_0(t) = \int_0^t K(t-s) dZ_s.$$

By the smooth-kernel semimartingale representation for non-singular Volterra processes, see for example [Abi Jaber et al. \[1\]](#), one has

$$d(X_t - x_0(t)) = K(0) dZ_t + \left(\int_0^t (K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) d(X_s - x_0(s)) \right) dt,$$

where \mathcal{R} is the first-kind resolvent of K . Hence

$$dX_t = (K(0)\kappa(\theta - X_t) + M_t + \dot{x}_0(t)) dt + K(0)\sigma\sqrt{X_t} dW_t,$$

with

$$M_t := \int_0^t (K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) d(X_s - x_0(s)).$$

Let

$$\tau := \inf\{t > 0 : X_t = 0\}.$$

On $[0, \tau]$, one has $X_s \geq 0$. For fixed t , the notation

$$d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s)$$

denotes the Stieltjes measure, in the variable s , associated with the function $s \mapsto (K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s)$. Since $-(K' * \mathcal{R})$ is non-increasing, the map $s \mapsto -(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s)$ is non-decreasing, and therefore

$$d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) \leq 0.$$

For $t \leq \tau$, Stieltjes integration by parts gives

$$\begin{aligned} -M_t &= -(K' * \mathcal{R})(0)(X_t - x_0(t)) + \int_0^t (X_s - x_0(s)) d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) \\ &= -(K' * \mathcal{R})(0)X_t + (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)x_0(t) \\ &\quad + \int_0^t X_s d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) - \int_0^t x_0(s) d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s). \end{aligned}$$

Since $X_s \geq 0$ and $d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) \leq 0$, the term involving X_s is non-positive. Thus

$$-M_t \leq -(K' * \mathcal{R})(0)X_t + (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)x_0(t) - \int_0^t x_0(s) d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s),$$

or equivalently,

$$M_t \geq (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)X_t - (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)x_0(t) + \int_0^t x_0(s) d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s).$$

Consequently, for $t \leq \tau$,

$$\begin{aligned} M_t + \dot{x}_0(t) &\geq (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)X_t + \dot{x}_0(t) - (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)x_0(t) + \int_0^t x_0(s) d_s(K' * \mathcal{R})(t-s) \\ &\geq (K' * \mathcal{R})(0)X_t + c_{K,x_0}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, up to τ ,

$$dX_t \geq (K(0)\kappa\theta + c_{K,x_0} - (K(0)\kappa - (K' * \mathcal{R})(0))X_t) dt + K(0)\sigma\sqrt{X_t} dW_t.$$

Let \underline{X} be the CIR process

$$\begin{aligned} d\underline{X}_t &= (K(0)\kappa\theta + c_{K,x_0} - (K(0)\kappa - (K' * \mathcal{R})(0))\underline{X}_t) dt + K(0)\sigma\sqrt{\underline{X}_t} dW_t, \\ \underline{X}_0 &= x_0(0). \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$2(K(0)\kappa\theta + c_{K,x_0}) > K(0)^2\sigma^2,$$

the classical strict Feller condition implies

$$\forall t > 0, \quad \underline{X}_t > 0.$$

By the one-dimensional comparison theorem for square-root diffusions, applied up to τ ,

$$\forall t \geq 0, \quad X_{t \wedge \tau} \geq \underline{X}_{t \wedge \tau}.$$

If $\tau < \infty$, then

$$0 = X_\tau \geq \underline{X}_\tau > 0,$$

which is impossible. Hence $\tau = \infty$, and therefore

$$\forall t > 0, \quad X_t > 0.$$

The proof is complete. \square

Remark 3 (Exponential kernel). For $K(t) = e^{-\eta t}$, $\eta \geq 0$, one has $\mathcal{R} = \delta_0 + \eta dt$ and $K' * \mathcal{R} = -\eta$. Hence $-(K' * \mathcal{R}) = \eta$ is non-negative, non-increasing and locally of bounded variation, and

$$c_{K,x_0} = \inf_{t \geq 0} (\dot{x}_0(t) + \eta x_0(t)).$$

In particular, for a constant input $x_0(t) \equiv x_0$, one has $c_{K,x_0} = \eta x_0$, and Proposition 2 gives non-attainment of zero whenever

$$2(\kappa\theta + \eta x_0) > \sigma^2.$$

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